

Large whale entanglements, strandings, ice entrapments and selective marine animal sightings reported to the Whale Release and Strandings Group in Newfoundland and Labrador and a summary of the Whale Release and Strandings Program during 2023

A Report to the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada –
Newfoundland and Labrador Region

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Acknowledgements

Thank you to local people from Heart's Delight and surrounding communities, and Dildo and surrounding communities, and the Bay Roberts and Witless Bay DFO fisheries officers for the much needed and greatly appreciated work in assisting us with the overwhelming task of coordinating rescue efforts for ice-entrapped white beaked dolphins during the spring. It seemed as if it was going on forever.

Thanks to the DFO fisheries officers from Witless Bay, St. John's and Marystown for their support in our searching for and disentangling four humpbacks this summer. It's an invaluable resource for us, to have worked with these professionals.

Thanks to Jackie Kean, Connie Dobbin-Vincent, and Jody Roach for their management of the program from DFO St. John's.

The Canadian Coast Guard Marine Traffic Centers diligently report entrapped and stranded marine animals and sightings regularly to the hotline. Thanks for the service.

To the harvesters of the Newfoundland Region who have continued to support the Whale Release and Strandings program throughout its long history, the success of our work releasing entrapped marine animals would not be possible without your continued support and participation.

Whale Release and Strandings Group

The Whale Release and Strandings Group (Tangly Whales, Inc.) is a non-profit environmental organization responsible for the disentanglement and response to strandings of marine animals in Newfoundland and Labrador since 2000 and incorporated in July 2002. The organization has a board of directors.

The Mission statement for the Whale Release and Strandings Group is:

- To conserve biodiversity
- To release whales from fishing gear
- To attempt to save fishing gear to the extent possible during a disentanglement
- To coordinate marine animal strandings responses
- To conduct research work on marine animals
- To conduct all other work on marine animals as seen fit.

From 1978 through 2023, assistance has been offered to harvesters in the Newfoundland Region who incidentally have large whales, leatherback sea turtles and basking sharks entangled in their fishing gear and for live stranded marine animals. This service has been provided with support and cooperation from Fisheries and Oceans, Canada.

Summary reports

During this time-period (1978-2023) information from harvesters regarding whale interactions has been recorded and monitored. Included are the incidences of entrapments, strandings and sightings of leatherback sea turtles, sharks and 20 different species of cetaceans that have been recorded in continuous reports and summaries from 1978 - 2023.

This represents the forty-seventh (47th) of such reports in a consistent format produced by the Whale Research Group and the Whale Release and Strandings Group. The purpose of these reports is to summarize yearly activities and important events, such as entrapments/entanglements/strandings/sightings of animals at risk and under study, research and/or educational activities undertaken. These entanglement reports are catalogued at the Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador Library (Centre for Newfoundland Studies), Fisheries and Oceans Canada, on Zenodo.org, and with the Whale Release and Strandings Group. One of the benefits of these reports is quick access to changes in entrapments and entanglements in the Newfoundland Region related to changes in fishing gear and distributions of large marine animals as well as the various

strandings, ice-entrapments and strandings and sightings of rare animals and animals under study.

Introduction

The disentanglement program, which has been run by the Whale Release and Strandings Group (WRS) from 2001-2023, plus providing during 2000 a one-year mentorship with the Canadian Coast Guard, uses methods of which the most important is working with stakeholders (harvesters) for disentangling of large whales from fishing gear, which was pioneered by Dr. Jon Lien (Lien 1980) and with a few modifications, these methods remain those of choice today.

The program in use today was designed and developed for the highly rural nature of over 800 fishing communities spread over the 17,000 km coastline of Newfoundland and Labrador (NL). The disentanglement assistance program has benefited harvesters, whales, leatherback sea turtles and the people of Canada. It provides assistance to often financially-strained harvesters, saving them thousands of dollars in what would be lost fishing gear and downtime if they did not have skilled support in releasing a large whale entrapped in their gear. It releases critically endangered leatherback sea turtles, large and often endangered whales and basking sharks from fishing gear and allows them to continue their life processes. We have the largest feeding population of humpbacks in the northwest Atlantic, with about 5,000 individuals visiting NL waters during spring, summer, and fall. These whales are the basis for a large tourism industry in the region.

The program also responds to all reported live and dead cetaceans and sea turtles, floating and stranded, as well as pack ice entrapments.

The purpose of the assistance is: (1) to assist harvesters in releasing whales from fishing gear, thus decreasing downtime and damage to fishing gear. The length of time a large marine animal is entrapped in fishing gear is directly correlated to greater gear damage and loss of income due to the gear not fishing properly or at all (Lien 1983), (2) to release entrapped marine animals as quickly and safely as possible to allow them to continue their life processes, such as feeding, migrating, mating, rearing their young, (3) to communicate with harvesters and communities about marine animals, including species at risk, habitat protection, and (4) to add to the scientific knowledge of cetaceans, leatherback sea turtles and sharks that inhabit Newfoundland and Labrador waters.

Fish harvesters have come to realize that calling a government sponsored program offers them a faster and more efficient alternative to dealing with a gear-entrapped animal than attempting a release on their own. Harvesters and untrained persons who take whales out of gear often leave large amounts of fishing gear on the animal perhaps because they do not or cannot look underwater to see all the gear that is on the entrapped animal. Whales caught in crab gear that are cut loose by harvesters and other untrained persons are often released with vast amounts of rope and pots still attached (Ledwell and Huntington 2001, 2002, 2006). This provides more opportunity for whale re-entrapment, further gear damage, and allows the animal to move from the vicinity in which it was initially entrapped. Free-swimming animals may be difficult to relocate, and/or difficult to catch

up with in order to remove the remaining gear left on it. A timely response by experienced personnel results in the removal of most, if not all, gear from the animals, minimal gear loss/damage and fishing downtime, particularly vital to the economically marginalized inshore harvesters.

From 1979 to 2023, two thousand and nineteen (2019) humpback whales (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), one hundred and sixty-four (164) minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*), fourteen (14) fin whales (*Balaenoptera physalus*), two North Atlantic right whales (*Eubalaena glacialis*), one bowhead whale (*Balaena mysticetus*) and eighty-eight (88) unknown large whales were reported entrapped or entangled in fishing gear in Newfoundland and Labrador.

Over the same period, eighty-two (82) leatherback turtles (*Dermochelys coriacea*) have been reported entangled in fishing gear in this region with a mortality of 25%. There have been seventeen (17) reported leatherback turtle strandings, with 13 of those being dead animals reported in the region. Two (2) live leatherbacks turtles that had stranded were rescued and returned to sea by members of the WRS group. A loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*) was collected cold stunned in Hermitage harbour and returned to ocean from the Harbour Breton harbour after it was rewarmed (Ledwell and Huntington 2007).

Entrapments, strandings and sightings of other cetaceans either unusual to the area or under study, or animals free-swimming but in poor health, and marine animals such as sea turtles, sharks, and walrus have also been documented (Lien 1994; Ledwell and Huntington 2000-2012; Ledwell, Huntington and Sacrey 2013-2015, Ledwell and Huntington 2016, Ledwell, Huntington and Enserink 2017, Ledwell, Huntington and Ledwell 2018, Ledwell, Huntington and Sacrey 2019, Ledwell, Huntington, Ledwell, and Landry 2021).

From 1992 to 2000, funding for a marine animal release program was varied and at times non-existent.

The most common types of fishing gear associated with entanglements in this region currently includes gillnets (cod, herring, mackerel, lumpfish, flounder, monk, skate and turbot) snow crab pots, whelk pots, toad crab pots, box traps (caplin, cod, herring, mackerel and squid), unspecified and illegal gillnets, ropes/buoys and moorings. In other words, most types of fishing gear have the potential to incidentally catch whales and they do. In recent years fishing effort in Newfoundland and Labrador has shifted offshore. This shift in gear has led to an increase in the number of offshore entrapments reported and offshore entanglements have primarily involved snow crab and whelk pot gear.

Methods

Whale, leatherback turtle and basking shark entanglements in fishing gear and strandings and sightings of marine animals were reported to the Whale Release and Strandings Program in 2023 by calling an advertised toll-free number (1-888-895-3003) which can be accessed 24 hours a day seven-days a week, year around. A trained release team responds by providing suitable, safe advice or sending expert personnel to the site for

needed assistance. The trained crew is equipped and ready to deploy immediately with an inflatable zodiac and necessary specialized tools for disentanglement of whales, leatherback sea turtles and basking sharks. The objective of each disentanglement is the safe, clean (complete) release of the whale or other marine animals from the fishing gear and minimal or no damage to the fishing gear involved in the entanglement. The disentanglement crew also responded to whale and leatherback turtle strandings. Calls concerning entanglements, strandings and dead floating animals were also forwarded to the group by harvesters, DFO Conservation Officers, Coast Guard Centers, Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP), Crime Stoppers and the public. Fisheries and Oceans Canada funded the program in 2023. Thank you to the Town of Portugal Cove-St. Philip's for their continued support.

Results and Discussion

Results of the Entrapment Assistance Program from previous years have been summarized in annual reports to Fisheries and Oceans and the Newfoundland and Labrador Department of Fisheries (Lien 1980; Lien and Aldrich 1982; Lien et al. 1982; 1983; 1984; 1985; 1986; 1987; 1988; 1989; Lien 1990; 1991; 1992; 1993; 1994; 1995; 1996; Ledwell, Huntington and Lien 2000; Ledwell and Huntington 2001; 2002; 2003; 2004; 2005; 2006; 2007; 2008; 2009; Ledwell, Huntington and Kelly 2010; Ledwell and Huntington 2011; 2012; Ledwell, Huntington and Sacrey 2013; 2014; 2015; Ledwell and Huntington 2016; Ledwell, Huntington and Enserink 2017; Ledwell, Huntington and Ledwell 2018; Ledwell, Huntington, Sacrey and Landry 2019; Ledwell, Huntington, Ledwell and Landry 2020; Ledwell, Huntington, Landry and Ledwell 2021, Ledwell, Huntington, Sacrey and Landry 2022).

Humpback Whales (Table 1)

There was a total of eleven (11) humpback whales (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) reported to WRS in 2023 that we could verify as having fishing gear on them or entrapped/entangled (Table 1). Four (4) of these WRS members released gear free. Throughout the year, as is the case every year, we get multiple reports of the same animals, or at least ones we believe to be the same animals, towing gear and we try to ascertain to the best of our ability by talking to the people who report it, which animals are which as we often do not get images. Individuals represented in Table 1 reflect which animals we determine to be entangled and do not represent the multiple reports we receive of the same whales reported with gear on them.

11th-12th June

A humpback was reported to WRS by a lobster fisherman entrapped between Sally's Cove and St. Paul on the West Coast at 20:48 on the 11th June. WRS geared up to respond, as the fisherman said he would be in the area at 0430 on the 12th June to check. WRS talked to the fisherman at 0900 who said he had not checked as he was still fishing. WRS asked DFO Rocky harbour to check the area. The fisherman call at 1600 on the 12th June to say he had talked to harvesters who had cut the whale out the gear. Neither he nor DFO officers could relocate the whale.

25th-26th June

Snow crab fisherman reported, to DFO on the 25th June, a humpback towing 2 large orange poly buoys off Gull Island Witless Bay on the Southern Shore of the Avalon. The wind was too strong for WRS to respond immediately, and we alerted the tour boats in the area to be on the lookout for the animal. At 1230 pm on the 26th June, a humpback towing 2 orange poly buoys was reported (to WRS) by a local swimmer close to shore. DFO fisheries officers and WRS searched the area, and after 4 hours discovered the whale close to Bay Bulls and heading SW. The wind was breezing up and we managed to shepherd the whale into calmer waters in Bay Bulls and removed all the gear including the 2 poly buoys and 20 meters of 9/16” rope at 1730. WRS talked to the skipper whose CFV number was on the buoys who said he had lost the gear in the Whale Deep on the Grand Banks on the 8th June. All the gear was returned to the harvester. We believe the whale from the 25th June to be the one from the 26th June.

29th-30th June

Humpback reported by a tour boat in Witless Bay on the Southern Avalon towing 2 large orange poly buoys and large amount of rope between the whale and the buoys and rope trailing behind the buoys. Whale reported accompanied with a calf. WRS members responded at 1500, and together with a tour boat from O’Brien’s tours, searched the area for 4 hours until dusk and could not relocate the animal. At 1515 on 30th June, the tour boats reported finding the entangled animal outside of the islands in Witless Bay/Mobile area. WRS responded with O’Brien’s tour boat, relocated the whale, removed a bridle wrap, the 2 poly buoys and 150 meters of rope. Disentanglement covered provincially and nationally by the CBC. The gear was returned to the harvester who said he lost it in the same area and time frame as the 25th-26th June animal.

9th-11th July

Harvester reported to WRS late evening of the 9th July of a humpback near South East Bight in Placentia Bay towing a yellow oblong buoy. He reported the whale was seen in the area multiple times. WRS responded on the morning of the 10th July with DFO fisheries officers from the Marystown detachment. We searched the area for 6 hours and were unsuccessful in relocating the animal. On the 11th July the whale was reported again close to the original sighting area. WRS members left at 1330 arriving in Petite Forte at 1645, hooked up with the same Marystown DFO officers in their patrol boat, searched the area, found and released the whale gear free just before dark. The phone number and CFV on the poly buoy belonged to a lobster fisherman from lobster fishing area 33 on the south shore of Nova Scotia. W. Ledwell talked to the harvester who said he lost the gear on the 10th May 2023 and believed another fishing or large vessel may have become entangled in it and cut it off. WRS members have released humpback whales with fishing gear on them from Nova Scotia and the Quebec Gaspe Bay area multiple times in the past. **(site reports)**

10th July

Humpback reported by fisherman tethered in snow crab gear off Cape St. Francis, Conception Bay. WRS second team responded with a DFO patrol boat out of Witless Bay and searched the area for several hours in foggy conditions but were unsuccessful in

relocating the animal. It is suspected that the animal freed itself of the gear, as it wasn't in the area marked by the harvester.

10th July

Humpback reported swimming SW at 1600 off of Cape Pine, St. Mary's Bay with rope embedded into its back. WRS members returning from the 10th July attempt to relocate the South East Bight whale stood by for further sightings of this animal but it was not relocated.

14th July

Humpback reported by hikers towing two small orange poly buoys off of Ferryland on the Southern Shore. Image sent to WRS showed the whale in the distance with one of the buoys behind its head and the other behind its tail. Because of the lateness of the report to WRS and due to the fact the whale was travelling offshore, no response was initiated. The animal was not relocated.

14th July

Humpback reported by hiker with netting over body. The hiker saw the whale on the 13th July, though didn't report it to WRS until the 14th July. No further sightings were reported of the animal.

18th July

Humpback towing rope off Quirpoon on the Great Northern Peninsula reported by a sailboat. No further sightings were reported of this animal.

29th July

Humpback reported by recreational cod fishers towing a large amount of rope off Brigus on the Southern Shore. WRS team worked on the whale trying to take the gear off of the animal for 3 hours as a cut had to be made at the jaw line. The gear was finally removed as the wind freshened. 67 meters of 9/16" poly rope was removed from the whale. No other gear was seen on the animal.

4th August

Brownsdale Harbour, two humpback whales reported entangled in a caplin trap. We asked for further information and if they had any photos. Although the whales were reported entrapped in a caplin trap, upon further investigation the whales were observed within 300m of trap, not in the trap. This is an example of getting people to provide more information to clarify what they see. We do not want to discourage reporting of what may be an entanglement, we seek further information to ensure that the entrapments really exist before going to the site.

7th August

Humpback towing large poly buoy and rope between St. Pierre and Miquelon. Recreational boater sent images of the buoy which included a CFV number, and the gear was traced back to an NL harvester from Port de Grave, Conception Bay. The harvester said it was from a snow crab set on the Grand Banks.

An interesting coincidence here is that a dead humpback was reported by the Canadian Coast Guard on the 14th August 9 nm from this reported entanglement. See 14th August in Table 4.

18th August

Sighted by 180NM off NL

Entanglement reported by DFO twin otter marine mammal observer crew. Pictures were taken but the whale was not seen again.

A rope bridle was caught through mouth of the whale. It was towing 2 poly buoys, one buoy from mouth to anterior pectoral, second buoy from fin on right side.

Minke whales (Table 2)

4th July

A minke (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) was reported in Holyrood, Conception Bay with a short section of rope draped over its body seeming to originate from its mouth. No further sightings of this animal were reported.

Ice entrapments

The spring of 2023 resulted in high mortalities for whales and seals in eastern NL (Table 4). Pack ice trapped an unknown number of white beaked dolphins (*Lagenorhynchus albirostris*) in Trinity and Conception Bays. Pack ice is considered natural mortality for white beaked dolphins here in NL, as the animals are common during every season and Trinity is a natural trap for them during southward moving pack ice. Dolphins being driven southward appear to turn into Trinity Bay and their escape route is blocked as the ice closes the Bonavista peninsula from the Conception Bay peninsula. As the ice moves up Trinity Bay the dolphins move ahead of it until finally, they are either forced ashore or trapped and killed in the ice. Although difficult to estimate, we believe over 100 white beaked dolphins died this spring in Trinity and Conception Bays. The animals die quickly when either forced ashore or crushed by the ice and responses must be immediate to capture and move them to ice-free open water.

Response is difficult to plan and coordinate, and relies heavily on the support and cooperative participation of local community members to activate a plan, with assistance, often simultaneously over the phone, from our group, as the dolphins, although healthy animals, as opposed to whales that strand freely which are for the most part going to die anyways, will succumb to the stress of the ice and being on shore unless removed immediately. Then these animals, if brought to nearby ice-free water may have some chance of survival, although we do not know the long-term effects on them from moving them under such stressful conditions (Ledwell and Huntington 2018). Ice-entrapped white beaked dolphins have been moved in this region to ice-free waters using snow mobiles, seal stretchers, tarps, sleds attached to ATVs, pickup trucks, and, in effect, any resource one can think of (Ledwell and Huntington 2004). It is truly remarkable the resourcefulness that exists in these communities, ingenuity from people used to thinking on their feet in emergency situations.

From the 10th March to the 7th April the WRS team, DFO officers and local community members were constantly working together with the ice-entrapped white

beaked dolphins. We were moving them, consulting community members on moving them, getting ready and preparing vessels and equipment to move them, monitoring both them and concerned community members, waiting for the dolphins to be forced ashore to move them, sheltering them in place until the ice shifted and watching them die in ice. We saved some, we learned a lot and, in the end, when the ice moved away, many others were discovered dead in the tidal zone that had died under the ice. Table 4 tells more details of that story.

Seals

We normally do not report seal strandings in our yearly reports, even though they represent, by far, the majority of calls we get every year. We talk to concerned citizens who see a seal hauled out and often explain to them that it is natural for the animals to be hauled out on a beach, wharf, slipway etc. We report all seal strandings to DFO who handle any injured animals. However, spring of 2023 was different. Hundreds of mostly young and multi age seals washed-up dead on beaches on the northeast Avalon and east Coast due to unstable pack ice and a period of strong NE winds. WRS was inundated with calls during April and May with lone live white coats observed on ice and beaches, and dead ones found on beaches and the concerns over disposals of their carcasses.

Strandings (Table 4)

1st May

A northern bottlenose whale (*Hyperoodon ampullatus*) washed ashore partially decomposed on the 1st May at Point au Mal on the Port au Port peninsula. The animal was approximately 7 meters in length. Rough seas in the area partially buried the animal in beach rock and we believe the animal washed back out. DFO was alerted and asked for necropsy funds by WRS, but none were available.

21st June

A 605 cm female Cuvier's beaked whale (*Ziphius cavirostris*) live stranded and died at Middle Arm in Green Bay on the 21st June. A necropsy was conducted by members of WRS. All tissue, organ samples, teeth and reproductive tract were collected and deposited to DFO Marine Mammals, St. John's.

15th September

A 522 cm female True's beaked whale (*Mesoplodon mirus*) live stranded and died at Rantem, Trinity Bay on the 15th September. Members of the WRS team conducted a field necropsy of the animal. WRS paid for the disposal of the necropsied whale and all samples including organs and teeth were deposited to DFO Marine Mammals, St. Johns.

14th-18th December

A 722 cm northern bottlenose whale (*Hyperoodon ampullatus*) live stranded between a floating dock and a large boulder wall on the 14th December at the Holyrood Marina. The animal looked emaciated with ribs and vertebrae showing. The whale was never grounded and although in deep enough water to be able to navigate out of the area and orientated by members of WRS, it chose to stay where it had stranded. WRS members monitored the whale for four days until it died. WRS explained to locals why the animal

did not want to move, the condition of the animal, the biology of the animal, its status and reasons why some animals strand. We asked DFO St. John's for permission to euthanize the animal because of the length of time it remained alive stranded, but that permission was not given. Tissue and teeth were taken by WRS, but no necropsy was conducted although WRS members were ready to do so.

Disentanglement workshops

The Whale Release and Strandings Group conducted marine mammal and sea turtle disentanglement workshops in Natuashish and Hopedale in Northern Labrador in 2023. Conservation officers from outlying communities attended the meeting in Hopedale. WRS gets sporadic reports of entangled whales in Northern Labrador (mostly minke) and often we gear up to respond but because of the distance the animals are not seen again or in some cases the animals are cut loose with a lot of unnecessary rope and netting on them. Because the gear used is light, with light anchoring methods, larger whales as humpbacks will easily tow the nets away, minke are the most common whales reported entangled. Part of our exercise included identification of the common whales seen in the area and the use of Tangly Whales standard cutting knife for disentanglement. We supplied each group with a standard cutting knife. WRS feel that now these officers can put a face to the NL Region group and have had a basic introduction to disentanglement techniques and they will contact us for further advice when an entanglement situation arises.

Education activities

Interactive presentations and display on north Atlantic whale species and leatherback turtles for children, youth and adults were presented at the following events: World Oceans Day NL, held at the Marine Institute and the Whale Festival at Cape Spear, hosted by Parks Canada. WRS had an interactive display table at the Cold Harvest 2023 Newfoundland and Labrador Aquaculture Industry Association (NAIA) 28th Conference and Trade Show. An additional presentation organized by Canadian Wildlife Federation (CWF) was adapted and delivered to a multi age group of both Winslowe Ridge Retirement Living residents and youth participants in CWF's WILD Outside program.

When a Cuvier's beaked whale live stranded and died at Middle Arm, Green Bay on the 21st June, schools were contacted in the community and invited to observe and engage with members of WRS as a necropsy was conducted. Teachers and students of all ages from MSB Regional Academy were eager to observe and ask questions throughout the necropsy and tissue sample collection process. CBC NL covered the event and interviewed teachers and students about their immersive "field trip-like" experience.

A similar educational opportunity arose, as is often the case with strandings in NL, when community members, including several children of varying ages, were very intrigued by the True's beaked whale that live stranded and died in their secluded community of Rantem, as several children, parents and grandparents looked on and asked questions pertaining to the biology of the whale, as well as the necropsy and scientific approach to the sampling process.

A member of the Whale Release and Strandings attended the Ropeless Consortium and the North Atlantic Right whale consortium. During this event the play ‘Between Breaths’ was presented in Halifax. This play is “inspired by the true story of Jon Lien – known as the Whale Man – *Between Breaths* is a profoundly emotional memory play that sails through Lien’s life and the dangerous, death-defying work of saving whales trapped in fishing nets off Newfoundland’s coast. Over his long career, Lien saved over 500 whales and earned the respect of the island’s fishermen...” (quoted from the playbill).

Manuscript in press:

Journal: Canadian Field Naturalist

Title: A review of beaked whale (Ziphiidae) stranding incidents in eastern Canada

Co authors: Don McAlpine, Tonya Wimmer, Wayne Ledwell, Pierre-Yves Daoust, Laura Bourke, Jack Lawson, Wotjtek Bachara, Zoe Lucas, Andrew Reid, Stephane Lair, Anthony Francois and Robert Michaud

Manuscript number: <http://doi.org/10.226621/cfnv137i2.2967>

Recommendations

Recommendation 1. Funding agreements should be in place with funds available before entrapment season begins. Agreements need to be established that are assurances to provide support to an organized program over a period of years. Programs that do not have these assurances will be very difficult to maintain and staff on an on-going basis (Lien 2004).

Recommendation 2. All licensed fishing vessels in the Newfoundland region should have stickers displaying the toll-free number onboard alerting them who to call when they encounter an entrapped or stranded whale in their gear or see an entrapped or stranded whale or leatherback sea turtle. By having the toll-free number visible in the wheelhouse, harvesters may decide to call for expert advice when they have or see a whale or leatherback entrapped and not attempt to cut animals free and leave them with large amounts of gear attached which may cause the animal to die or become re-entrapped. This situation can be at least partially avoided if boats have the entrapment assistance hot line number easily visible onboard and upon calling can be advised on the proper release procedures or be advised that a release team is available to attend to the entanglement. This may lessen the number of whales or sea turtles each season swimming around with large amounts of snow crab and other gear attached. See Appendix I for toll-free sticker.

Because of the dangers inherent in fishing boats encountering entangled large whales in their fishing gear in the offshore, especially snow crab gear, fishing groups need to be advised by an experienced disentanglement group on procedures to protect lives and lessen gear entanglements.

Table 1. Humpback whales reported entangled in fishing gear in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2023

Date	Area	Gear type	Description
11 th June	Sally's Cove, Gulf St. Lawrence 49.79N, 57.90W	Lobster	WRS geared up to respond but whale was cut out of the gear by fishermen and not seen again
25 th June	Witless Bay, Southern Shore 47.30N, 52.76W	Towing 2 medium size red poly buoys	Weather too windy to respond immediately by water. WRS searched area by binoculars but unable to relocate whale
26 th June	Petty Harbour- Bay Bulls, Southern Shore 46.32N, 52.34W	Towing 2 medium size red poly buoys	WRS released the whale gear-free after tracking it from Petty Harbour to Bay Bulls recovering the 2 poly buoys and 20m 9/16" snow crab rope
29 th June	Witless Bay, Southern Shore 47.24N, 52.76W	Towing 2 medium size red poly buoys	Whale towing balloons attached to long rope. WRS searched area for 4 hours but unable to relocate animal
30 th June	Witless Bay, Southern Shore 47.24N, 52.76W	Towing 2 medium size red poly buoys	WRS released all gear from whale, which included the 2 poly buoys and 170 m of 9/16" snow crab rope
9 th July	South East Bight Placentia Bay 47.22N, 54.32W	Towing yellow oblong buoy close to the animal	Reported late evening, no resighting of animal
10 th July	South East Bight Placentia Bay 47.22N, 54.32W	Towing yellow oblong buoy close to the animal	WRS and DFO searched area for 7 hours but animal not relocated
10 th July	Cape St Francis, Conception Bay 47.82N, 52.78W	Snow crab gear	Whale reported anchored in snow crab gear by fishermen. WRS second team and DFO searched area where it was reported, though animal had moved from area. Fog set in and further searching area north and south could not relocate animal
10 th July	Cape Pine, Trepassey Bay 46.61N, 53.52W	rope	Humpback with deep cuts over back swimming south reported by hiker. Unable to relocate animal
11 th July	South East Bight Placentia Bay	Towing yellow	Whale from 10 th July resighted in same area. WRS and DFO searched area late

	47.22N, 54.32W	oblong buoy close to the animal	into evening and found and disentangled whale gear-free. Whale was towing lobster gear from the south shore of Nova Scotia
14 th July	Ferryland, Southern Shore 47.02N, 52.85W	2 red poly buoys and rope	Whale towing one poly buoy behind head and one behind tail. Reported by hikers. Images sent. Whale moving SE. DFO and WRS prepared for response, but because of lateness of reporting, stood down
14 th July	Cape Spear 47.52N, 52.62W	Netting	Hiker spotted whale towing net on evening of 13 th but reported it on 14 th . Animal not resighted
18 th July	Quirpoon, Great Northern Peninsula 51.38N, 55.26W	Rope	Reported by sailboat moving north. Image sent. Whale not relocated
29 th July	Brigus South, Southern Shore 47.11N, 52.87W	9/16 poly rope	Whale disentangled gear-free, removing 67 m of 9/16" poly rope by WRS
4 th August	Brownsdale Harbour, 48.04N, 53.11W	Two humpback whales reported entangled in a caplin trap	Reported entrapped in caplin trap, later only observed within 300m of trap.
7 th August	Between St. Pierre and Miquelon in position 46.38N, 56.03W	Towing poly balloon	Gear (snow crab) traced back to NL harvester. Animal not relocated.
18 th August	180NM off NL 45.12N, 49.49W	Bridle through mouth, towing 2 poly boys, one mouth to anterior pectoral, second buoy from fin on right side	Reported by DFO twin otter observer crew. Pictures taken. Not seen again.
18 th August	Fortune Head 47.08N, 55.86W	Thrashing fin	Reported by light housekeeper. Many people viewing from shore, could be an orca killing a whale. Pictures too far to

			determine exact happening.
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Table 2. Minke whales reported entangled in fishing gear in Newfoundland and Labrador in 2023.

Date	Area	Description
4 th July	Holyrood, Conception Bay 47.39N, 53.13W	Whale had rope over rostrum and trailing a few feet behind animal. WRS responded but unable to relocate

Table 3. Leatherback sea turtle strandings/sightings reported in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2023

Date	Area	Description
15 th June	St. Georges, South West Coast 48.43N, 58.49W	Dead and very decomposed. Probably dead since last fall. WRS members on call for necropsy but called off by DFO due to state of decomposition.
11 th September	Long Harbour. Placentia Bay 47.25N, 53.49W	Animal reported close to shore by Vale nickel plant. Not resighted.
24 th October	St. Lawrence, Placentia Bay 46.54N, 55.23W	Decomposed with missing flippers. Washed out before response could be carried out by WRS
28 th September	Cape St, Francis, Conception Bay 47.49N, 52.47W	Reported entangled or injured by harvester. WRS geared to respond, but images sent to DFO were verified by WRS that what they were looking at was a leatherback eating a large Lion's mane jellyfish

Table 4. Ice-entrapped, stranded and dead floating cetaceans reported in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2023

Date	Area	Species	Description
23 rd January	Change Islands, Notre Dame Bay 49.67N, 54.42W	Sperm	10m dead sperm. Local: "Don't know the type, but it's a big outfit"
6 th February	Point May, Fortune Bay 46.90N, 55.95W	Pilot	Dead on beach

10 th March	Heart's Delight, Trinity Bay 47.77N, 53.46W	White-beaked dolphins	Approximately 20 white-beak being forced ashore by pack ice. WRS, locals and fisheries officers respond in monitoring and moving them
11 th March	Heart's Delight, Trinity Bay 47.77N, 53.46W	White-beaked dolphins	Approximately 20 white-beaks in middle of bay amongst the pack ice. Icebreaker in area of dolphins
15 th March	Conception Harbour, Conception Bay 47.46N, 53.20W	White-beaked dolphins	Attempt by WRS and DFO to rescue white-beaks in the bay amongst pack ice using small inflatable. Dolphins disappeared as rescuers were working their way through the pack ice toward them
15 th March	Spaniards Bay, Conception Bay 47.62N, 53.27W	White-beaked dolphin	Dolphin died after being forced ashore as DFO fisheries officers were on scene for rescue attempt
16 th -17 th March	Carbonear-Harbour Grace, Conception Bay and Heart's Content, Trinity Bay 47.73N, 53.21W 47.87N, 53.37W	2 White-beaked dolphins	2 dolphins relocated from Carbonear to Harbour Grace had to be moved again as ice closed in. One trucked across Tilton Barrens to Heart's Content but died on release
18 th March	Carbonear, Conception Bay 47.74N, 53.23W	33 White- beaked dolphins	Animals discovered dead on beach after pack ice has moved off into the bay
27 th March	Holyrood, Conception Bay 47.39N, 53.14W	5 White-beaked dolphins	Forced into small cove by pack ice. Rescuers WRS, DFO and locals put plan in place to move dolphins to ice-free water of Bay Bulls. Dolphins disappear into ice just prior to being forced ashore
28 th March- 2 nd April	Dildo, Trinity Bay 47.57N, 53.56W	15-20 White- beaked dolphins and 3 humpbacks	Ice-entrapped, but still with enough ice-free water to swim and surface freely
29 th March	Dildo, Trinity Bay 47.57N, 53.56W	Approximately 15 White- beaked dolphins	In small body of water with murre, puffins, loons, and sea ducks
30 th March	Dildo, Trinity Bay	15 White-	Being forced ashore by pack

	47.57N, 53.56W	beaked dolphins	ice. WRS, locals and DFO corral and move 3 to Placentia, Placentia Bay, 6 dolphins corralled and left secured by boat marina with ice blocked and held off by ropes and chains
31 st March	Dildo, Trinity Bay 47.57N, 53.56W	6 White-beaked dolphins	Locals without advice from WRS or DFO, release barrier set on 30 th March and drive dolphins out into open water as ice had moved off from the cove
31 st March	Bishops Cove, Conception Bay 47.64N, 53.23W	1 White-beaked dolphin	Dead on beach
31 st March	Greens Harbour, Trinity Bay 47.64N, 53.51W	6 White-beaked dolphins	Animals reported late in the evening in small pool of water surrounded by pack ice. WRS members searched area early morning of 1 st April but were unable to locate any of these animals
1 st April	Dildo, Trinity Bay 47.57N, 53.56W	6 White-beaked dolphins	Pack ice moves back in and dolphins from 31 st succumb to it
2 nd April	Dildo, Trinity Bay 47.57N, 53.56W	1 White-beaked dolphin	Local uses his longliner to clear ice from one of one of the animals from the 30 th March rescue attempt
3 rd April	Winterton, Trinity Bay 47.96N, 53.33W	2 White-beaked dolphins	Ice-entrapped, but still with enough water to swim in. DFO responds
4 th April	Winterton, Trinity Bay 47.96N, 53.33W	2 White-beaked dolphins	White beaks from 3 rd April not seen by DFO fisheries officers, but ice-free water area has expanded in area they were seen
7 th April	Seal Cove, Conception Bay 47.47N, 53.08W	2 White-beaked dolphins	Dead on shore
24 th April	New Ferolle, Great Northern Peninsula 51.03N, 57.06W	Sperm whale	Dead on shore
27 th April	Middle Cove, Avalon Peninsula 47.66N, 52.69W	Sperm whale	Dead in wash of beach. Appeared to have been dead for weeks
1 st May	Port au Port Peninsula, West Coast	Northern bottlenose whale	Approximately 7 meters long. Decomposed and partially buried in beach rock. No

	48.55N, 58.72W		samples taken
22 nd May	Isle aux Morts, South West Coast 47.59N, 59.98W	Minke	Dead in cove. Images sent for WRS to ID
21 st June	Middle Arm, Green Bay 49.70N, 56.10W	Cuvier's beaked whale	605 cm female live stranded and died. Necropsy conducted by members of WRS. Reproductive tract and samples sent to DFO
18 th July	Gros Morne 49.63N, 57.96W	Harbour porpoise	Dead on beach
20 th July	Brownsdale, Trinity Bay 48.06N, 53.09W	Sperm whale	Freshly dead, drifting 3 nm off Brownsdale. Images sent. Notice to Mariners sent out.
23 rd July	Off Placentia, Placentia Bay 47.16N, 54.05W	Possible humpback	Dead drifting reported by large ship, "Dream Catcher" to Placentia Coast Guard
28 th July	Between LaPoile and Rose Blanche, South West Coast 47.38N, 58.28W	Large whale species	Dead drifting. Notice to Mariners sent out. Images sent to WRS, but unable to ID species
See 4 th August?			
6 th August	Nameless Cove, Great Northern Peninsula 51.31N, 56.73W	Minke	Dead stranded, "stinking up" Nameless Cove
7 th August	Tilting, Fogo Island North East Coast 49.71N, 54.06W	Humpback	Dead floating against cliff face
14 th August	St. Pierre 46.47N, 56.04W	Humpback	~15m humpback dead floating. WRS passed the info on to DFO for surveillance flight.
15 th September	Rantem, Trinity Bay 47.69N, 53.86W	True's beaked whale	522 cm female live stranded and died. Necropsied by members of WRS. Samples sent to DFO St. John's
16 th September	Davidsville, Gander Bay 49.36N, 54.44W	5 dolphins, unconfirmed species	Live stranded. Locals pushed 3 back out. 2 seen dead. Unsure of survival of others. WRS asked DFO to respond, but animals were either dead or not seen when they arrived. WRS unable to obtain images, but suspect white-sided dolphins

17 th November			
4 th December	Pleasantville, North East Coast 49.51N, 55.44W	Possible minke	Dead on beach. Locals want it moved for fear of “stinking place up”
14 th -18 th December	Holyrood, Conception Bay 47.39N, 53.13W	Northern bottlenose whale	Live stranded and died after four days

Table 5. Miscellaneous marine animals reported in Newfoundland and Labrador during 2023

Date	Area	Species	Description
1 st May	Chapels Cove, Conception Bay 47.44N, 53.13W	Walrus	Dead stranded on beach. Images sent to WRS
6 th July	Long Harbour, Placentia Bay 47.38N, 53.93W	Humpback	Animal reported by boater as ‘sickly looking’ and maybe entangled. WRS and DFO searched area, but could not relocate animal. No whales in the area
15 th July	Fortune Harbour, North East Coast 49.51N, 55.22W	Beluga	Adult beluga in harbour. Images sent
26 th July	Musgrave Harbour, North East Coast 49.45N, 53.95W	Beluga	Free swimming near Banting Provincial Park beach
11 th August	Peters River, Saint Mary’s Bay 46.76N, 53.61W	Thresher shark	Fresh dead on beach. DFO fisheries people alerted by WRS
11 th September	St. John’s Harbour 47.56N, 52.70W	Large whale species	Swimming around St. John’s harbour reported by Coast Guard traffic. WRS responded, but were unable to see the animal. Grainy images sent by CG Traffic but unable to ID whale
23 rd September	St. Vincent’s Beach St. Mary’s Bay 46.77N, 53.62W	Porbeagle shark	Fresh dead stranded. WRS notified DFO fish people
3 rd October	Upper Amherst Cove Bonavista Bay	2 North Atlantic right	Either 2 rights or bowheads seen off the

	48.55N, 53.24W	or bowhead whales	cove. The images sent to Jack Lawson DFO were too poor for definite ID
24 th October	Botwood, Notre Dame Bay 49.14N, 55.34W	2 Sunfish	Dead stranded. Information passed onto DFO by WRS
1 st November	Manuels, Conception Bay. 47.52N, 52.97W	North Atlantic right whale	Right whale "Freckles" free swimming. Images and video sent to WRS and DFO

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WHALE AND TURTLE NOTICE

1-888-895-3003

If you have a WHALE or TURTLE or basking shark (live or dead) caught in your fishing gear, call this toll-free number and we will respond with a trained team. If you see any whales, turtles or dolphins (live or dead) on a beach, please call. Should you see any leatherback sea turtles please call.

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Appendix II

